

Farmers considered the damage to be a result of the unexpected drought and took no protective measures.

Infestation started in patches and spread to entire fields. The infested plants became stunted; leaves started to turn yellow and to dry. In severely infested fields, tillers were covered with thousands of nymphs and adults, giving them a whitish, waxy coating. The insect outbreak may be attributed to the inordinate delay of the monsoon rains during the growth phase. The infestation was reduced after the rains. Farmers were advised to spray phosphamidon (0.05%) or dimethoate (0.03%), or to apply carbofuran (0.5 kg a.i./ha) or phorate (1.2 kg a.i./ha) granules.

IRRI 1976 insecticide evaluation results available

The results of laboratory and field evaluation of insecticides conducted at IRRI in 1976 are available. The report includes not only results of coded and named insecticides but also results of various methods of application. The report can be obtained free of charge by writing the Head, Department of Entomology, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Rice insect pests in Laos

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The insect problems of rice in landlocked Laos, where a single crop of predominantly local, glutinous varieties is grown, were investigated in 1973–75. Insect populations were generally low. Insecticide control was usually not required and probably not economically feasible.

The most common pests on upland rice were the Bombay locust *Patanga succincta* L. and the bugs *Nezara viridula* L. and *Leptocoris* spp. In contrast, those insects were uncommon on lowland paddy rice, which had more of the smaller grasshoppers *Oxya* and *Euscirtus* spp. in the seedbeds, and stem borers *Sesamia inferens* (Walk.) and *Chilo* spp. in the transplanted rice. Few rice gall midges *Pachydiplosis oryzae*

(Wood-Mason) or whorl maggots *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino were found.

Few cicadellids and delphacids were found on the local rice varieties; small, experimental plots of IR varieties were often more heavily infested with *Nephotettix* spp. and *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål.

Stem flies in Haringhata, Nadia, West Bengal, India

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Four stem flies, *Atherigona indica* Mall, *Oscinella* sp., *Steleocerus ensifer* Thom, and *Gaurax* sp., belonging to the families *Anthomyiidae* and *Oscinidae* (Diptera), were found responsible for extensive damage to rice seedlings in upland rice nurseries of four rice varieties.

Damage, starting after the seedlings were about 3 weeks old, was visible even 3 weeks after transplanting. The usual symptoms were the withering of central leaves, yellowing of leaf sheaths, and root rot.

Mortality among young seedlings in field nurseries may even reach 50% in a transplanted experimental plot it was 33%.

Infestation rates in the different varieties of the aus and aman rices tested were significantly different. A maximum of 9.5% infestation was found in the variety Kalma 222 of *aman* rice. In the Dular variety of *aus* rice, the rate was only 0.7%. Different stem fly species were never found on the same plant.

Occurrence of a mite in Tainan District, Taiwan

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Sterility of rice is epidemic in Tainan District during the second crop and causes extensive damage. It has occurred for some time now but its cause is still unknown. Recently, while examining rice ears and sheaths under a microscope, we unexpectedly found many mites. The density of adults and eggs was high.

The mite *Steneotarsonemus madecassus* is new to Taiwan. It could be the major cause of the sterility. Farmers, however, have not been aware of its importance.

Some 2,000 ha have been infested with *S. madecassus* in Tainan District. About 20 percent of the crop was seriously damaged. All varieties except indicas were attacked. The outbreak may be attributed to high levels of synthetic organic phosphorus insecticides applied to rice, and to prohibition of the use of synthetic organic hydrochlorinated insecticides. As one of the phoretic mites, *S. madecassus* may be spread by insects or other arthropods.

Note: Anyone who has observed a similar problem is invited to write to the editor or to Mr. Ou. Replies to IRRN may be published.

A note on the chemical control of *Dichdispa armigera* Olivier in a rice nursery

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Because *Diadisa armigera* Olivier has been a serious pest of rice since 1970 in all the coastal districts of Andhra Pradesh, India, the effect of various chemicals (granular and spray) against hispa in the nursery was studied. Tested in granular form were chlorpyrifos, basudin, carbaryl-lindane, disulfoton, phorate, monocrotophos, endosulfan, BHC, fenthion, chlorfenvinphos, and quinalphos. Tested in sprays were fenitrothion, dichlorvos, phosphamidon, Ambithion, carbofuran, and monocrotophos. The granular formulation was applied with the seed. The germination rates of seed, the phytotoxic effects of the chemicals, and the mortality of the beetles released on the germinated seedlings were recorded. Length of root and shoot, number of leaves, and wet and dry weights were measured. The foliar chemicals were sprayed 15 days after sowing. Beetles were released on the seedlings 15 days after sowing; their mortality was recorded daily up to 35 days after sowing.